

DESIGN, OPTIMIZATION AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF CRANKSHAFT

Bhalerao Ganesh Nandkumar

P. G. Student, Department of Mechanical (Design Engineering) SVCET Rajuri, Pune, Maharashtra, India
* bhalariaoganesh35@gmail.com

Dr. Zope Sanjay Bhaskar

Principal and Guide, Sahyari Valley College of Engineering & Technology Rajuri, Pune, Maharashtra, India
* s.b.zope.99@gmail.com

Patil Amol Ramesh

Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, SVCET Rajuri, Pune, Maharashtra, India
* pamol19@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Crankshaft is a crucial component in an engine assembly. Crankshaft is consisting of two web sections and one crankpin, which converts the reciprocating displacement of the piston to a rotary motion with a four link mechanism. Generally crankshafts are manufactured using cast iron and forged steel material. In this work to design and finite element analysis of crankshaft of 4 cylinder petrol engine of Maruti swift Vxi. of 1200 cubic capacity. The finite element analysis in ABAQUS software by using six materials based on their composition viz. Cast iron, EN30B, SAE4340, Structural steel, C70 Alloy steel and Aluminium based composite material reinforced with silicon carbide & fly ash.

The parameter like von misses stress, deformation; maximum and minimum principal stress & strain were obtained from analysis software. The results of Finite element show that the Aluminium based composite material is best material among all. Compare the result like weight and Stiffness parameter. It is resulted of 65.539 % of weight, with reduction in deformation.

KEYWORDS: Crankshaft, ABAQUS, Optimization, Material Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In Internal Combustion Engine Crankshaft play an important role to convert the reciprocating motion of piston in to rotational motion with the help of four link mechanism. Crankshaft is must be strong enough to take the downward force of the power stroked without excessive bending so mostly the life and reliability of engine is depend on the strength of crankshaft. In Internal Combustion engines, the transient load of maximum cylinder gas pressure is transmitted to crankshaft through the connecting rod, However Crankshaft convert reciprocating motion of the piston along with connecting rod to the rotating system of components. Due to torsion the dynamic load and rotating system exerts continues repeated bending and shear stress on crankshaft, which are common stresses acting on crankshaft and it is mostly responsible for crankshaft fatigue failure. Hence, fatigue strength and life assessment is an important phenomenon in crankshaft development. In crankshaft crankpin is behave like a beam with a distributed load along its overall length that varies with crank position. In crankshaft design of each web right and left handed are like a cantilever beam subjected to bending and twisting. Bending causes tensile and compressive stresses. Twisting causes shear stress and due to shrinkage of web onto the journal compressive stresses are set up in journal and tensile hoop stresses in the web. Initially we select materials for crankshaft for analysis are Structural Steel, SAE 4340, EN30B, Cast Iron, C-70 Alloy Steel. After FEA analysis we select one of the best material considering parameters like Deformation (mm), Maximum value of mass (Kg), Max Principal Stress (N/mm^2), Maximum Principal Strain, Von Misses Stress (N/mm^2) Maximum Value.

Rajesh M. Metkar. [1] Their work is based on comparative studies of two methods of fatigue life assessment of a single cylinder diesel engine crankshaft. One is fracture mechanics approach by linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) and other is recently developed critical distance approach (CDA). These methods shows crack growth, time required for failure and other parameters essential in life and reliability of crankshaft. Analysis is done in Ansys and nCode commercial software, Analysis result are also been used for predicting the fatigue life but are based on the stress and strain method, hence are not been used for comparative fatigue life prediction.

Adeknle A. [2] design a shaft under various load conditions using Computer Aided Design, and results obtained are proved that it saves wastage of materials, time consumption in FEA of crankshaft, and a software program was developed using the formulas initially derived and a numerical procedure for computing the deflection using the double integration methods.

Solanki [3] present the research work on crankshaft design and optimization. Selection of materials, manufacturing process for crankshaft, failure analysis, design consideration etc. are studied. In design of crankshaft considers the dynamic loading condition and optimization of shaft satisfying the requirements of the automobile specification with minimize cost and size effectiveness. Their conclusion is the crack grows faster on the free surface while the central part of the crack front becomes straighter. Fatigue is the main factor for failure of the crankshaft.

Rinkle Garg, Sunil Baghla [4] they work on a cast iron single cylinder engine crankshaft. A static analysis is done on a cast iron crankshaft. 3D model of crankshaft is created in Proe software. FEA is done and obtain result shows the variation of the stress magnitude at critical location. Obtained results are used in optimization of crankshaft. They conclude the strength of the crankshaft as the maximum limits of stresses, total deformation and strain is decreased. The weight of the crankshaft is also decreased by 3934 gram also decrease the inertia force. Weight reduced hence the cost of crankshaft is reduced and increase the engine performance.

Yingkui and Zhibo [5] they create a three dimensional model of a diesel engine crankshaft by using Pro E software. The finite element analysis is done in ANSYS under extreme operation conditions and giving the boundary condition stress distribution regions are found on the crankshaft surface. The crank stress change model and suggest the improvement method for the crankshaft structure design. Their research work shows that the high stress region mainly concentrates in the Knuckles of the crank arm & the main journal, and the crank arm and the connecting rod journal, which is the area most easily broken.

Balamurugan. [6] His work on modelling and optimization analysis of crankshaft and estimate the compressive study of the fatigue performance. They compare two crankshafts, cast iron and forged steel, from a single cylinder four stroke engines. Finite element analysis is done an obtained result are shows the variation of stress magnitude at critical point. The dynamic analysis is done analytically and results are verified by simulation in ANSYS tool. In the optimization process geometry changes compare with the current engine, fillet rolling and results in increased fatigue strength and reduced cost of the crankshaft, without changing connecting rod and engine block. Analysis results in testing the crankshaft under static load containing stresses and deformation. Forged iron crankshaft is able to withstand the static load, it is concluded that there is no objection from strength point of view also, in the process of replacing the cast iron crankshaft by forged steel crankshaft

DESIGN OF CRANKSHAFT

For the theoretical calculation of crankshaft we consider the configuration of Maruti Swift Vxi 4-cylinder petrol engine to calculate the theoretical static result:

Table No.:- 1 Specification of 4 Cylinder petrol Engine

SR. NO.	Type	4 Cylinder Petrol engine (Value)
1	Capacity of engine	1200cc
2	Number of cylinder	4
3	Bore × Stroke	86 × 68 mm
4	Compression Ratio	18:1
5	Maximum power	8.1hp @ 3600rpm.
6	Maximum Torque	16.7Nm @ 2200 rpm.
7	Maximum gas pressure	25 bar or 2.5 N/mm ² .

When the crank has turned through 35° from the top dead center, the pressure on the piston is 1 N/mm² and the torque on the crank is maximum. The ratio of the connecting rod length to the crank radius is 4. Assuming suitable data when is required. We design the crankshaft for two position of the crank.

DESIGN OF THE CRANKSHAFT WHEN THE CRANK IS AT AN ANGLE OF MAXIMUM TWISTING MOMENT

Force on the Piston,

$$F_p = \text{Area of the bore} \times \text{Maximum combustion pressure}$$

$$F_p = \frac{\pi}{4} \times D^2 \times p' = \frac{\pi}{4} (86)^2 \times 1 = 5808.8N \quad (1)$$

In order to find the thrust in the connecting rod (F_Q), we should first find out the angle of inclination of the connecting rod with the line of stroke (ϕ).

We know that,

$$\sin \phi = \frac{\sin \theta}{l/r} = \frac{\sin 35^\circ}{5} = 0.1147$$

$$\therefore \phi = \sin^{-1}(0.1147) = 6.58^\circ \quad (2)$$

We know that thrust in connecting rod,

$$F_q = \frac{F_p}{\cos \phi} = \frac{5808.8}{\cos 6.58^\circ} = 5847.3N \quad (3)$$

Thrust on the crankshaft can be split into tangential component and the radial component.

Tangential force acting on the crankshaft,

$$F_T = F_Q \sin(\theta + \phi)$$

$$F_T = 3880.45N \quad (4)$$

And Radial force,

$$F_R = F_Q \cos(\theta + \phi)$$

$$F_R = 4373.7N \quad (5)$$

Due to tangential force (F_T), there will be two reactions at the bearings 1 and 2, such that

$$H_{(T1)} = \frac{F_T \times b_1}{b} = 3880.45 \times 86 / 172$$

$$H_{(T1)} = 1940.22N$$

$$H_{(T2)} = \frac{F_T \times b_2}{b} = 3880.45 \times 86 / 172$$

$$H_{(T2)} = 1940.22N \quad (6)$$

Due to radial Force is given by, Reaction at bearing (a & b)

$$H_{(R1)} = \frac{F_R \times b_1}{b} = 4373.7 \times 86 / 172$$

$$H_{(R1)} = 2186.85N$$

$$H_{(R2)} = \frac{F_R \times b_2}{b} = 4373.7 \times 86 / 172$$

$$H_{(R2)} = 2186.85N \quad (7)$$

Now the various parts of the crankshaft are designed such as:

Design of crankpin:-

Let, d_c = Diameter of the crankpin in mm;

We know that the bending moment at the center of the crankpin,

$$M_c = (H_{R1}) \times b_2 = 2186.85 \times 86 = 188069.1N - mm \quad (8)$$

And the twisting moment on the crankpin,

$$T_c = (H_{T1}) \times r = 1940.22 \times L / 2 = 65967.48N - mm \quad (9)$$

∴ Equivalent twisting moment on the crankpin,

$$T_e = \sqrt{(M_c)^2 + (T_c)^2}$$

$$T_e = \sqrt{(188069.1)^2 + (65967.48)^2}$$

$$T_e = 199303.02Nmm \quad (10)$$

We know that,

$$T_e = \frac{\pi}{16} \times (d_c)^3 \times \tau$$

$$199303.02 = \frac{\pi}{16} \times (d_c)^3 \times 35 \quad (\text{Assume } \therefore \tau = 35Nmm)$$

$$\therefore d_c = 30.72mm \quad (11)$$

Since this value of crankpin diameter (i. e. $d_c = 30.72$ mm) is less than the already calculated value $d_c = 44$ mm . We shall take $d_c = 44$ mm .

Design of Crank against Fatigue Loading:

According to distortion energy theory,

Voin misses stress induce in crankpin,

$$M_{ev} = \sqrt{(K_b \times M_c)^2 + \frac{3}{4}(K_t \times T_c)^2}$$

Where, K_b =Combine Shock and fatigue factor for bending=2

$K_t = \text{Combine Shock and fatigue factor for torsion} = 1.5$

$$M_{ev} = \sqrt{(2 \times 188069.1)^2 + \frac{3}{4} (1.5 \times 65967.48)^2}$$

$$M_{ev} = 385.776 \text{ KN} - \text{mm} \quad (12)$$

Where, $\sigma_v = \text{Voin-misses stress}$

$$M_{ev} = \frac{\pi}{32} \times (d_c)^3 \times \sigma_v$$

$$385.77 \times 10^3 = \frac{\pi}{32} \times (44)^3 \times \sigma_v$$

$$\sigma_v = 16.12 \text{ N} / \text{mm}^2 \quad (13)$$

Now,

$$T_{ev} = \sqrt{(K_b \times M_c)^2 + (K_t \times T_c)^2}$$

$$T_{ev} = \sqrt{(2 \times 188069)^2 + (1.5 \times 65967.48)^2}$$

$$T_e = \frac{\pi}{16} \times (d_c)^3 \times \tau$$

$$388.936 = \frac{\pi}{16} \times (44)^3 \times \tau$$

$$\tau = 6.25 \text{ N} / \text{mm}^2 \quad (14)$$

RESULTS:-

- Diameter of the crankpin = 44 mm
- Length of the crankpin = 33 mm
- Diameter of the shaft = 60 mm
- Web thickness (both left and right hand) = 35 mm
- Web width (both left and right hand) = 65 mm

FEA OF CRANKSHAFT

CATIA modelling software is used to create 3D model of crankshaft with the help of slandered dimension.

Figure No.:-01 Two Dimensional View of crankshaft.

Figure No.:- 02 3D modelling of Crankshaft using CATIA

A) Material Details for static structural analysis

Table No.:- 02 Material Properties used for analysis

INPUT				
Sr. No.	Material	Young's Modules(N/mm ²)	Poisson ratio	Density (kg/mm ³)
1	Structural Steel	2.10E+05	0.277	7800
2	SAE 4340	1.90E+05	0.270	7676
3	EN 30B	2.05E+05	0.300	7740
4	Cast Iron	1.78E+05	0.300	7197
5	C-70 Alloy Steel	2.07E+05	0.300	7700
6	Aluminium Composite	0.70E+05	0.33	2611

Figure No.:- 03 Meshing of crankshaft by method

Meshing of crankshaft for static structural analysis is shown in Fig. 5-5 Solid 187 mesh element and element size is (0.0025 mm) is used for the meshing to improve the mesh quality.

Number of Nodes: 117439

Number of Elements:-69613

B) Apply Load and boundary condition.

Boundary conditions play an important role in finite element analysis. Crankshaft is constricts with a ball bearing from one side and with a journal on other side. The ball bearing is press fit to the crankshaft and does not allow the crankshaft to have any motion other than rotation about its main axis. Since 180 degrees of the surface facing the load 1500 N in downward z direction constricts the motion of the crankshaft.

Figure No.:- 04 load and boundary condition applied on crankshaft.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A) Analysis

For the finite element analysis 15KN Force is used. The analysis is carried out ABAQUS software. The maximum and minimum von-misses stress, deformation, Maximum and minimum principal stress and strain

Table No.-03 Results of Von misses, Deformation, Weight

Sample No.	Material Identification	Maximum Von Misses (N/mm ²)	Maximum Deformation (mm)	Maximum Principal Stress (N/mm ²)	Maximum Principal Strain (N/mm ²)	Mass (Kg)
1	Caste Iron	4.73E+01	5.59E-03	1.29E+01	1.61E-04	4.421
2	EN30B	4.73E+01	4.95E-03	1.29E+01	1.43E-04	4.589
3	SAE 4340	4.89E+01	5.26E-03	1.20E+01	1.55E-04	4.712
4	Structural Steel	4.86E+01	4.81E-03	1.29E+01	1.40E-04	4.792
5	C 70 Alloy Steel	4.73E+01	4.75E-03	1.29E+01	1.39E-04	4.73
6	Aluminium Composite	4.55E+01	1.02E-03	1.29E+01	2.86E-04	1.413

Out of six material the aluminium composite material meeting the maximum parameter and according to minimum deformation it is suggest the suitable material for crankshaft

1. VON-MISES STRESS 2. DEFORMATION

Figure No.- 05 Von Misses Stress (Aluminum Composite material) of Crankshaft. Figure No.- 06 Deformation of (Aluminum Composite material) crankshaft

3. MAXIMUM PRINCIPAL ATRESS 4. MAXIMUM PRINCIPAL STRAIN

Figure No.-06 Maximum Principal Stress (Aluminum Composite material) of crankshaft Figure No.- 07 Maximum Pricipal Strain (Aluminum Composite material) of crankshaft

SUMMARY OF COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS:

- Material aluminium composite is meeting the maximum no of requirements.
- The minimum available deformation and the difference between the minimum deformation available and the deformation when aluminium composite is used, is 0.001022 mm which is too less & can be ignored.

- Though it is not confirming the minimum mass of the body, the difference between the minimum mass available & the mass when Aluminium Composite is used, is 1.63 Kg which can be neglected to get the optimum design.
- Aluminium Composite will give optimum results as compared to the other materials given in the case study.

VOLUME WEIGHT AND STIFFNESS OF THE CRANKSHAFT

Compare the computational analysis result of two material C 70 Alloy Steel and Aluminium Composite we define the following parameter.

a) Weight of crankshaft

- For C 70 Alloy Steel material.

The volume of connecting rod is used is 6.143e-04. Therefore the mass of the crankshaft for respective material is

$$\text{Weight} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}$$

$$\text{Weight} = 6.143e-04 \times 7700$$

$$\text{Weight} = 4.73 \text{ Kg.}$$

- For aluminium composite material.

The volume of connecting rod is used is 6.143e-004. Therefore the mass of the crankshaft for respective material is

$$\text{Weight} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}$$

$$\text{Weight} = 6.143e-04 \times 2612$$

$$\text{Weight} = 1.63 \text{ Kg.}$$

b) Stiffness of the crankshaft

- For C 70 Alloy Steel material.

$$\text{Weight of crankshaft} = 4.73 \text{ Kg}$$

$$\text{Deformation} = 0.00475 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = \text{Weight} / \text{Deformation}$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = 4.73 / 0.00475$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = 995.78 \text{ kg/mm}$$

- For aluminium composite material.

$$\text{Weight of crankshaft} = 1.63$$

$$\text{Deformation} = 0.001022$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = \text{Weight} / \text{Deformation}$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = 1.63 / 0.001022$$

$$\text{Stiffness} = 1594.912 \text{ kg/mm}$$

CONCLUSION

1. Weight can be reduced by changing the material of the current materials
2. The optimized crankshaft is 65.539 % lighter than the current crankshaft material.
3. The new optimized crankshaft is comparatively much stiffer than former C 70 Alloy Material.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rajesh M. Metkar, Vivek K. Sunnapwar, Subhash Deo Hiwase, Vidya SagarAnki, Mahendra Dumpa "Evaluation of FEM based fracture mechanics technique to estimate life of an automotive forged steel crankshaft of a single cylinder diesel engine", Procedia Engineering 51 (2013) 567 – 572
- [2] A.A. Adekunle, "Development of CAD Software for Shaft under various Loading Conditions", Procedia Engineering 38 (2012) 1962 – 1983
- [3] A. Solanki, K. Tamboli, M.J, M.J, M.J, M.J. Zinjuwadia, (2011), "Crankshaft Design and Optimization- A Review" National Conference on Recent Trends in Engineering & Technology.
- [4] Rinkle Garg, Sunil baghala "finite Element and anylisis and optimization of crankshaft design" International jornal of engineering and management research, Vol2 Issue6 December 2012.
- [5] G. Yingkui, Z. Zhibo (2011), "Strength Analysis of Diesel Engine Crankshaft Based on PRO/E and ANSYS" Third International Conference on measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation, pp 362-364.
- [6] C. M. Balamurung R. Krishnaraj, M. Sakthivel. K. Kanthavel, D. Marudanchalam. R. Palani, (2011), "Computer Aided Modeling and optimization of Crankshaft" International Journal of Scinetific & Engineering Reserch, Vol 2, issue8.
- [7] Kuldeep B, Arun L. R. "Analysis and optimization of Connecting Rod using ALFASiC composites" International Journal of Inovation research in Science, Engineering and Technology. Vol.2 Issue 6 June 2013.